

Amylase crystalloids in a cystic lesion of the parotid gland diagnosed by fine needle aspiration cytology

Cengiz Kocak^{*,1}

^{*}Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine, Usak University, Usak, Turkey.

ABSTRACT Several types of crystalloids, including tyrosine, collagenous, intraluminal, and amylase crystalloids, may be encountered in fine-needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) of salivary glands. They have been reported in benign and malignant lesions of the salivary glands. Amylase crystalloids mainly found in benign salivary gland lesions. Microscopic identification of the crystalloids is made according to differences in structural appearance. As it can help in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant salivary gland lesions, it is vital to identify types of crystalloid. In this report, a 73-year-old man with painless mass in the left parotid gland is presented. Ultrasonographic examination demonstrated a well-defined, hypoechoic lesion in the tail portion of the left parotid. Microscopic examination of smears revealed many non-birefringent, rectangular, rhomboid and rod-shaped with parallel sides crystalloids varying in size. Crystalloids stained pink with Hematoxylin & Eosin (H&E), bright orange with Papanicolaou (PAP), and deep blue with May Grunwald Giemsa (MGG). Inflammatory cells and rare benign ductal epithelial cells were observed in a mucoid background. The cytopathological diagnosis was reported as a benign non-specific cystic lesion with amylase crystalloids. Since amylase crystalloids are only seen in benign lesions of the salivary glands, it is essential to distinguish between amylase and the other crystalloids.

KEYWORDS Amylase, crystalloids, cytology, fine needle aspiration, parotid gland, salivary gland

Introduction

Crystalloids may be encountered in fine-needle aspiration biopsy (FNAB) of salivary glands. Several types of crystalline structures such as amylase, tyrosine, collagenous, oxalate, and intraluminal crystals have been described in neoplastic and non-neoplastic salivary gland lesions. Although very rare, crystalloids have been reported in both benign and malignant lesions. Microscopic identification of the crystalloids is made according to differences in structural appearance [1,2]. Thus, since it can guide in differentiating benign and malignant lesions, it is essential to identify the type of crystalloid.

In this paper, we present a case of benign non-specific cystic lesion containing the amylase crystalloids in FNAB of the parotid gland in a 73-year-old man.

Case report

A 73-year-old man was admitted to the department of radiology with a complaint of a painless mass in the left parotid gland. The history of the patient was unremarkable, and the physical examination was normal. Ultrasonographic examination demonstrated a well-defined, hypoechoic lesion in the tail portion of the left parotid, measuring 15 × 10 mm. Given the clinical and radiological features, prediagnosis of the patient was considered as a lymphoepithelial cyst in the parotid gland. Ultrasound-guided FNAB was performed according to standard procedure using a 22-gauge needle. About 1.0 cc of a mucoid, cream-coloured fluid was aspirated. The aspirated fluid was smeared using a liquid-based monolayer cytology method (Becton Dickinson SurePath PrepStain Slide Processor, Becton Dickinson Diagnostics, Burlington, USA). Smears were stained with routine Hematoxylin & Eosin (H&E), Papanicolaou

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¹Department of Pathology, Faculty of Medicine Usak University, 1 Eylül Campus, 64000, Usak, TURKEY; Email: dcengizkocak@hotmail.com

(PAP), and May Grunwald Giemsa (MGG) stains. Microscopic examination of smears revealed many geometric, multifaceted non-birefringent crystalloids varying in size. The crystalloids were rectangular, rhomboid and rod-shaped with parallel sides (Fig. 1). They stained pink, eosinophilic with H&E (Fig. 1A), bright orange with PAP (Fig. 1B) and deep blue with MGG (Fig. 1C). Inflammatory cells and rare benign ductal epithelial cells were observed in a mucoid background. The cytopathological diagnosis was reported as a benign non-specific cystic lesion with amylase crystalloids. The patient did not undergo any surgical procedure. There was no growth of the mass in the one year's follow-up after the diagnosis.

Fig. 1. **A:** H&E-stained smear showing numerous pink crystalloids accompanied with numerous inflammatory cells and rare, rare benign ductal epithelial cells, x 200. **B:** PAP-stained smear showing bright orange rectangular and rhomboid crystalloids with pointed ends, x 100. **C:** MGG-stained smear showing rhomboid, non-birefringent, and dark blue crystalloids, x 200.

Discussion

Takeda and Ishikawa first demonstrated amylase crystalloids in a salivary duct cyst, and they suggested that crystalloids may result from the amylase of saturated saliva [3]. Jayaram et al. first described amylase crystalloids in FNAB smear from a parotid cyst [4]. Yada et al. suggested that the presence of a cystic space, reflecting salivary stasis, seems to be essential for the formation of the crystalloids [5]. It is essential to differentiate other types of crystalloids from amylase crystalloids because different types of crystalloids can be seen in malignant salivary gland tumours [6]. Whereas amylase crystalloids can be associated with nonneoplastic and neoplastic salivary gland diseases such as sialolithiasis, benign salivary gland tumours [7], sialadenitis [8], lymphoepithelial cyst, and [9]. Until now, amylase crystalloids have not been presented in any malignant tumour of the salivary gland in the literature. Therefore, the occurrence of amylase crystalloids in FNAB smears of the salivary gland favours a benign lesion [6].

Amylase crystalloids in salivary glands can be recognized by routine staining methods such as PAP, H&E, and MGG stains. High amylase activity in cystic fluids can be assessed using biochemical methods [10]. In light microscopic examination, amylase crystalloids appear as non-birefringent, geometric, polygonal, rhomboid-shaped structures ranging between 5 μ and 500 μ in size. They are stained orange with PAP, dark blue with MGG, and pink with H&E stain [11]. Whereas, collagenous crystalloids appear as radial and fusiform, birefringent, eosinophilic needle-shaped fibres of collagen on H&E stain. They are reported to be seen in pleomorphic adenomas, myoepitheliomas, and myoepithelial carcinomas [1,2,11]. Tyrosine crystals appear as a non-birefringent, eosinophilic, refractile, sunburst or petal shaped structure with blunt ends on H&E stain. They are mainly encountered in pleomorphic adenomas and malignant salivary gland neoplasms [1,2,6,12,13]. Intraluminal crystalloids

appear as dense amorphous eosinophilic material, and they are described in malignant salivary gland tumours [2,13].

Consequently, the presence of crystalloids in FNAB of salivary glands should be examined carefully, because it is crucial to identify types of crystalloid as it can help in the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant salivary gland lesions. Also, an accurate diagnosis of these lesions from FNAB samples of salivary gland would be guided to clinicians in avoiding from unnecessary surgical intervention.

Competing Interests

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